

CURE DEGREE MONITORING OF AN INFUSION PROCESS BY DEFORMABLE ELECTRONIC CIRCUIT WITH INTEGRATED CAPACITIVE SENSORS

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we present our latest progress in applying deformable electronic circuit for the cure degree monitoring of a resin infusion process. Recently, a demand for more complex composites geometry accompanied with novel materials is seen for composites industry. Because of this, composites manufacturer is encountered with increasing difficulties of production, assembly and maintenance of it. Applying a system to monitor these stages can clearly solve the issue. However, because of the irregular 3D shapes, traditional electronic circuit that is flat and rigid is becoming impractical for use. Thus, to achieve the deformability of the system, the idea is to divide the circuit into smaller functional blocks that are individually non-deformable, and interconnect them via horseshoe-like deformable interconnections. As a result, the circuit as a whole can be deformed while maintaining its electrical functionality and reliability. The developed sensor system is able to withstand deformation caused by the manufacturing process where changes of pressure and internal strain will happen.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are quickly expanding their territory into many industries that are traditionally dominated by heavy metal materials, such as aeronautics/aerospace, construction, wind energy, automotive [1-4] and so on. Because of a demand for more complex geometry in combination with newer materials, a big challenge is imposed to composites manufacturers for the production, assembly and maintenance of it. Due to this, a method that is able to monitor and control these different stages is highly desired. However, traditional electronic circuits are mostly flat, either in a rigid or flexible format, making them difficult to be used in a novel 3D geometry. In this study, our latest progress of a deformable microsystem for *in situ* cure degree monitoring of a glass fibre reinforced plastic (GFRP) fabricated by a resin infusion process is presented. Interdigital type of capacitive sensor is designed, fabricated and embedded for monitoring different manufacturing steps, especially the cure degree of composites. Curing phase is certainly an important stage during manufacturing of a composite component, during which the polymer constitute of composites cross-links, results in the consolidation of the whole composite structure. By controlling the curing phase one can obtain a superior quality component and, therefore, will increase the reliability and optimize the design of the part, leading to a decrease of the lifecycle cost. To accommodate the irregular shape of the composites, the idea is to combine flexible, yet non-deformable functional island containing the sensor with the deformable horseshoe-like interconnections. The circuit comprises flexible islands, where the island holds and

contains a single capacitive sensor for cure degree monitoring. The developed sensor system is flexible and deformable, and is able to withstand the deformation caused by the manufacturing process where large and sudden change of air pressure is happening.

2 CAPACITIVE SENSOR AND DEFORMABLE CIRCUIT

Fig. 1 Interdigital capacitive sensor's (left) schematic drawing and (right) in-house made sample

During the curing of the epoxy resin matrix composite, the dielectric properties of the resin change dramatically. The resin starts as monomers or oligomers in a liquid state with low viscosity. The conductive ionic impurities, introduced during synthesis or preparation of the resin, are able to move freely within the resin. As the polymerization progresses, the crosslinking between monomers or oligomers continues and a 3D polymer network is formed and expanded. The formation of a polymer network/chain influences the change in permittivity. Furthermore, the resin becomes solid, highly viscous, thus the motion of the ion impurities is limited, and a drop in capacitance is expected. By monitoring the dielectric properties of the resin, we can monitor different phases occurring during the curing. Fig. 1 (left) shows the schematic drawing of the capacitive sensor: w stands for the width of each 'finger', g stands for the gap (spacing) between fingers, and L stands for the finger length. When an electric potential is applied between the anode ($V+$) and cathode ($V-$) of the sensor, an electric field is created between the fingers, and extended to the space on both sides of the finger structure to a certain distance. This depth (distance), that the majority of the electric field is able to reach, is termed the penetration depth of the sensor, and determined by the spatial wavelength ($w+g$) of the structure [5]. Fig. 1 (right) shows the interdigital type of capacitive sensor used in this study fabricated by printed circuit board technology. The sensor fabrication starts from patterning a polyimide-copper laminate into interdigital structure by lithography and spray etching process, afterwards a thin coating of Organic Solderability Preservative (typical thickness 0.15-0.3 micron) is applied on top of the copper electrode to protect it from oxidation. The w and g used in this study are $100\mu\text{m}$, and the L is 15mm . The resulted sensor is $68\mu\text{m}$ in thickness ($50\mu\text{m}$ PI + $18\mu\text{m}$ Cu), and $15\text{mm}\times 12\text{mm}$ in total size.

The emergence of stretchable electronics technology has enabled a wide range of applications, such as personal healthcare, polymer waveguide, and smart textile [6-10]. Future sensor system should also be deformable to arbitrary 3D shapes to accommodate the complex geometry and novel manufacturing process of the composites, this means the sensor system should survive the deformation whereas still maintaining its performance and reliability during and after the deformation. To achieve such systems, either the material or the structure must stretch. Novel intrinsically stretchable nano-material has been a dominant study for this field, such as carbon nanotubes, graphene and metal-nanowires. However, their low conductivity compared to conventional conductive material is still one of main disadvantages. Very high manufacturing cost compared to established technology is another

disadvantage. Printed Circuit Board based stretchable electronics technology possesses the advantages of cheap manufacturing cost and high electrical performance. The idea is to interconnect flexible, yet non-deformable functional islands containing the sensor unit or other intelligence with the deformable interconnections [6]. Note that deformable, instead of stretchable, is used as the terminology here, to differentiate dynamic multi-cycle stretchability from semi-static deformability which happens mostly during a composite manufacturing process. In this study, we investigated a simple sensor system with one single island interconnected to the external sensor readout via horseshoe-shaped interconnections as shown in Fig. 2. Gradual transitions in width of the copper and corresponding supporting polyimide reduce the local strain in the copper during the deforming [5]. To demonstrate the deformability of this sensor system, a vacuum assisted resin infusion process for fabricating the FRP is selected and will be elaborated later.

Fig. 2 Capacitive sensor in combination with horseshoe-like stretchable interconnections

3 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

In this study, a vacuum assisted resin infusion process for fabricating the GFRP is investigated by a deformable electronic circuit comprising capacitive sensor and stretchable interconnections. During the fabrication process, the change of the processing pressure, and internal strain change due to curing would lead to deformation of the embedded electronic system. Six layers of UDO ES 500 UD Glass Fibre reinforcements were laid up on top of a flat glass mould, a flexible and deformable interdigital and temperature sensor (not shown in Fig. 2) system were embedded between reinforcing glass fibres. Additionally, there was one thermocouple outside the mould for ambient temperature measurement. The plate was sealed on the four edges with vacuum bag. The epoxy matrix system (from Momentive) in use is a two-part system consisting of the EPIKOTE MGS RIMR 135 resin and the EPIKURE MGS RIMH 137 hardener. 300g of RIMR135 and 90g of RIMH137 were thoroughly mixed by a mechanical blender, degassed, and infused to the vacuum bagging through the resin inlet, the outlet was connected with a tube to the vacuum line, and once the resin reaches the outlet, both tubes were clamped to stop the resin flow and keep the bag under vacuum. The glass fibre reinforced composite was cured at room temperature for 24h, followed by a post cure in the oven at 80 °C for 16h as recommended by the datasheet. A self-made readout system comprising a microcontroller unit was designed and fabricated for the capacitance and temperature measurement. A National Instrument USB acquisition card was used for the ambient temperature measurements, and data were logged through a Labview-based controlling software on PC. After the experiment, the measurement result was plotted by MATLAB.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 3: Capacitance and temperature data along the room temperature cure

During the course of cure, the capacitance and temperature within the resin change accordingly. The capacitance measurement for the resin cured at room temperature is shown in Fig 3. At the beginning of cure, a large increase in capacitance was identified at the beginning of cure, indicating that the resin has reached the capacitive sensor and completely covered the capacitive sensor. The large increase in capacitance is caused by the change of the dielectric layer above the sensor from air to resin as well as the ionic impurities in the resin. As the cure progresses, cross-linking between monomers or oligomers is continued and the polymer network keeps growing. The resin system becomes more viscous and the ionic diffusion gets restricted. The restricted ionic diffusion results in a decrease of capacitance. At around 12 hours into the cure, a relatively steep decrease in capacitance is observed indicating the transition of the resin from a gelly state into a glassy state, and is referred to gelation point or vitrification point [11]. As the resin becomes more viscous during the curing, the translational diffusion of ion and the rotational diffusion of dipole moment are not able to follow the excitation signal, and needs longer time for the reorientation and relaxation. On the other hand, the temperature measurement gives almost stable value during the 24h cure. No conclusion on cure degree can be drawn from temperature measurement.

During post-curing, the heating up of the oven leads to an increase in resin temperature as shown in Fig. 4. A large increase in capacitance is observed in the beginning of post curing, the overshoot of capacitance possibility indicates further polymerization within the resin. After the peak, capacitance values decrease and saturate to nearly stable values since the oven is kept at 80°C. After 16h, the oven is turned off. The decrease in temperature causes the drop in capacitance, as the dielectric property is temperature dependent. However, the change in absolute value is considered insignificant compared to the peak observed at the beginning of post-curing or change during the curing stage. As can be seen from the plot, the capacitance measurement gives information about resin cure that is mostly related to degree of cure rather than the influence of the ambient environment. Again, the temperature measurement reveals little information on cure degree. What we got from the plot is purely the influence of the oven. In fact, the temperature plot follows nicely with the program configured in the oven, only with a small delay in time owing to the heat insulation of epoxy.

Figure 4: Capacitance and temperature data along the post cure in the oven

9 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we presented our latest status of the development of a deformable microsystem for *in situ* cure degree monitoring of a glass fibre reinforced plastic fabricated by a resin infusion process. The developed sensor system combines flexible, yet non-deformable islands containing the functional unit (capacitive sensor for cure degree monitoring in this case) with deformable horseshoe-shaped interconnections. During the vacuum assisted resin infusion process, fabricated sensor system is stable throughout the fabrication process. Thanks to the stretchable interconnections, the system is able to withstand deformation coming from the fabrication process, i.e. the change of pressure and resin internal strain.

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